

Refining the Critical Obstetrical Debriefing Process: A Quality Improvement Project

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Background

- Pregnancy related deaths or other obstetrical complications significantly impact those involved on an emotional level
- Debriefing sessions can provide emotional support for those that experience a critical obstetrical incident
- A debriefing can help healthcare providers feel supported and less stressed, as well as assist in their emotional recovery

Significance

- Critical obstetrical incidents (COIs) can cause burnout, secondary traumatic stress, and compassion fatigue, which can lead to high turnover among nurses
- Emotional stressors have been identified as key contributors for nurses leaving their positions
- Poor communication and poor teamwork can account for as much as 70% of COIs in obstetrical units
- Debriefing process can help improve teamwork, assist with potential safety threats, and provide coping skills to nurses who experience COIs

Purpose

The purpose of this DNP project was to:

- Refine the debriefing process that occurs after a critical obstetrical incident
- Improve compassion satisfaction
- Decrease compassion fatigue
- Promote emotional recovery among the staff after a COI

Methods

- Setting:** 68-bed Women’s Center at a Regional Medical Center in Southern California
Participants: 216 licensed personnel who work in Labor and Delivery/Postpartum unit
Interventions: Provide remote education related to compassion satisfaction, compassion fatigue, secondary traumatic stress, burnout, and the significance of debriefing
Measures:
- Debriefing tool analysis
 - Professional Quality of Life 5 (ProQOL 5) survey to assess baseline compassion satisfaction, compassion fatigue, secondary traumatic stress, and burnout levels
 - Debriefing satisfaction survey to assess barriers leading to incomplete debriefing sessions

Theoretical Framework

Results

Discussion

- Debriefing completion rate after COI was 87.5% and incompleteness rate was 12.5%
- Moderate level of compassion satisfaction noted post implementation in participants
- Low level of burnout and secondary traumatic stress seen for both pre and post implementation
- Participants (41.7%) reported debriefing sessions should be held at the “end of the shift”
- Participants (75%) reported an immediate debriefing session could improve the satisfaction of doing future debriefing sessions
- Common themes reported as debriefing barriers were: increased acuity due to pandemic, limited staff, lack of time, and patient assignments

Limitations

- Small sample size
- Covid 19 pandemic resulted in increased number of personnel taking a leave of absence
- Fluctuation of census and staffing
- Remote education required due to in-person restrictions

Recommendations

- Quarterly assessments of debriefing sessions
- Provision of continued self-care resources for staff to sustain compassion satisfaction levels
- Larger sample size and conduct in-person education sessions
- Providing nurses and health care providers a debriefing process can continue to support their mental well-being